

AGROFORESTRY, CAP AIMS AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Fostering sustainability

THE WHAT AND WHY

Sustainability of land use systems

In Europe, agriculture generates 44 million jobs in the food chain, provides food security for 500 million consumers, and stewards 48% of EU Land. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is the main policy driver for agriculture in Europe and aims to provide not just food for European citizens (Cork 2.0 Declaration) but also compliance with global strategic policies such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2015). At the Meeting on “Sustainability Challenges delivering the 2030 Agenda” the EU showed that the first three priorities of the Seventh European Action Programme (EAP) corresponded to the UN SDGs: (1) “protect, conserve and enhance the Union’s natural capital” (SDG 6, 14-15), (2) “develop a resource-efficient, green and competitive low-

carbon economy” (SDGs 7-9, 11-13) and (3) “safeguard the Union’s citizens from environment-related pressures and risks to health and well-being” (SDGs 2-3). These 3 priorities have been deployed into nine CAP objectives, namely: ensure a fair income to farmers, increase competitiveness, rebalance the power in the food chain, climate change action, environmental care, preserve landscapes and biodiversity, support generational renewal, vibrant rural areas and protect food and health quality. The CAP objectives changed from the exclusive increase of food to a more sustainable agriculture and will be based on 9 objectives in the Post-2020 period that can be reached, among others, through the implementation of Agroforestry.

Agroforestry contributes to sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources.

Wall, Nico

European Economic and Social Committee thematic session on the CAP. European Economic and Social Committee (EESC).

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

Agroforestry as a tool for sustainable land use management

The Agenda 2000 reforms started the division of the Common Agricultural Policy into a “first pillar” (based on single farm payments) and a “second pillar” focused on rural development measures. Payments in Pillar I are completely funded from the European Union, while Pillar II payments are partly-funded by national governments (between 50 and 85% depending on the country). Following the CAP reform in 2003, payments were decoupled from the production of a specific product, with farmers instead receiving payments based on a set amount per hectare of agricultural land. The CAP has also aimed to become more environmentally-oriented. For the 2007-2013 period, Pillar I across the EU27 was worth just over three times as much as Pillar II. The

Agroforestry measure 222 appeared and provided support for agroforestry within the forestry measures within the EU, but it was not appropriately designed (Santiago-Freijanes et al. 2018). For the 2014-2020 period, rural development and environmental issues account for close to 24% of the total CAP budget and coupled payments were decreased and the description and aims of the agroforestry measure, the so-called measure 8.2 were improved also after the OMNIBUS regulation. Now, the EU is preparing the CAP Post 2020 where result-based payments will be key to foster the implementation of agroforestry in Europe in both Pillar I and Pillar II as agroforestry is one of the land management practices able to fulfill the objectives of the future CAP.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727872.

Keywords: Pillar I, Pillar II, CAP Post 2020

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HIGHLIGHTS

Agroforestry importance within the CAP has been increased in the last decades, but there is still a lot of land use that will be sustainably improved through the implementation of AF.

AF is able to fulfill the objectives of the CAP post 2020 to support viable farm income and resilience across the Union to enhance security, foster to sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

Agroforestry and the objectives of the CAP Post 2020

Agroforestry contributes to the CAP aim of support viable farm income and resilience across the Union to enhance security through the optimization of the farm use of the resources including water and sun and the provision of farm multiple products including those replacing fossil fuels and new products associated to the bioeconomy development. Moreover, agroforestry practices increases production per hectare of multiple products and reduce the needs of external inputs. The CAP aim related with fostering to sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air linked to a more efficient soil management can be associated to agroforestry that increases biomass production per unit of land and therefore the inputs of organic matter into the soil thanks to the better use of the sun radiation but also by increasing the surface soil nutrients as the nutrients placed in deeper soil layers are placed in the soil surface. Agroforestry also contributes to the CAP aim related to climate change mitigation and adaptation as well as sustainable energy as the last report IPCC Global Warming of 1.5 °C report already recognizes that agroforestry is one of the mitigation and adaptation options related to land use and ecosystems while providing biomass based renewable energy sources. The CAP aim of contribute to the protection of biodiversity, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes is also fulfilled by agroforestry land use as agroforestry is able to protect and increase biodiversity thanks to the heterogeneity it creates, but also enhance provision, ecological and cultural ecosystem services. The CAP aim related to improve the farmers position in the value chain is tackled through the increase of products delivered from the farm that allows farmers cooperatives to have a better position in the value chain and be more resilient to climate and market changes. The aim related with the key objective of promote employment, growth, social inclusion and local development in rural areas, including bio economy and sustainable forestry can be reached through the farm competitiveness increase caused by agroforestry through the multiple products delivered from the same land associated to new market opportunities at local level associated to bioeconomy, this will also improve the development of business plans and the establishment of young farmers in rural areas therefore the establishment of vibrant rural areas.

Chestnut agroforestry system in Galicia (NW Spain).
Rodríguez-Rigueiro, FJ

FURTHER INFORMATION

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OCTOBER 2018

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